

THE STATUS OF THE MANAGEMENT FUNCTIONS AND PRACTICES OF THE SECONDARY SCHOOL HEADS IN CALACA DISTRICT: BASIS FOR ENHANCED ACTION PLAN

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ABSTRACT

The principals being the key figures in the schools are well-equipped with both managerial skills and competencies. Excellent exercise of this principal's empowerment leads to attainment of management effectiveness, and thereby successful fulfilment of Thus, this scenario prompted the researcher being a secondary principal, to conduct a study on how secondary school principals/school heads work their management functions and practices. Through this study, an enhanced action plan was designed. The whole school environment, most specifically for the student. The study aimed to assess the status of management functions and practices of the secondary school principals in Calaca District with the end of preparing an enhanced action plan. This study used the descriptive method of research as it aimed to assess the extent of performance of the school heads in practicing management functions and self-made questionnaire was used to gather the data. The results showed that among the management functions such as planning, organizing, staffing, directing and controlling, the last in rank in the assessment made was controlling. With this result, it can be concluded that the enhanced action plan will focus on this function.

Keywords: Education, Management Functions, Descriptive Method, Philippines